

MEDICAL SCIENCES

Arkhmammadova Gulshan Mubariz

Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, Assistant

Rustamov Elshan Anvar

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Hasanova Vafa Agahan

Department of Orthopedic Dentistry assistant

Azerbaijan Medical University

Baku, Azerbaijan

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QUALITY OF REMOVABLE AND FIXED DENTURES MADE OF THERMOPLASTIC.

Abstract.

In recent years, dentistry has been developing by leaps and bounds - this includes implantology, gnathology, and digital dentistry. By mastering these serious, necessary, correct areas and introducing them into our practice, we raise the status of our clinics and our level of proficiency in the profession to the proper height. Despite this, removable dentures are still relevant. The most popular are removable structures made of thermoplastics.

Key words: *removable denture, flexibility and strength, advantages and disadvantages.*

Recently, technologies for manufacturing removable and non-removable structures from thermoplastics have appeared on the dental market. The general characteristics of thermoplastics are determined by the name itself - "material that is plastic when heated," that is, these materials acquire the required shape in a heated state without the use of monomers. Back in the 50s of the last century, the search for non-toxic and hypoallergenic materials for the manufacture of removable dentures began in the USA. As a result of research work, such materials were identified - thermoplastics. They had a biologically neutral reaction, that is, they did not have a toxic or allergic effect on the body. In addition, a high degree of plasticity, the ability to remember shapes, precision in manufacturing, and the presence of a wide range of light make it possible to expand the possibilities of partial and complete prosthetics, splinting, manufacturing immediate dentures, gingival dentures, splint prostheses and improve their aesthetic qualities. An indispensable material in the manufacture of removable structures is nylon. Before we talk about the advantages and disadvantages of nylon prostheses, it is necessary to remember what kind of material it is. For more than half a century, nylon production has not changed. 1953, New York - the date and place of birth of nylon - the material of the future, as they once said. The father of the material was the English chemist Carothers, and the industrial mother was the giant Du-bon. Carothers named the fiber Neylon in English in honor of New York - the birthplace of the discovery and his homeland - London. The starting material is caprolactam, a short-molecule monomer that is melted at high temperatures and converted into a long-molecule polymer. The resulting threads are pulled in such a way that their length increases five times, and the monomer molecules line up, as if on a ruler, along the fiber, which gives the thread additional strength and lightness. These qualities of nylon are advantageous in the manufacture of removable structures. Let's return to the pre-

sent and find out what are the advantages and disadvantages of nylon prostheses in comparison with acrylic and metal ones. Nylon prostheses are more flexible and elastic, but at the same time boast increased strength. Flexible dentures have a precise fit and secure retention. They are held on the gums by means of dento-alveolar nylon clasps, which are also made of silicone, which makes them invisible in the oral cavity. When installing them, there is no grinding of the teeth, and the teeth do not become loose during use of the prosthesis. Another undoubted advantage of nylon is its inability to absorb moisture. This means that microorganisms simply cannot settle in it. While acrylic is simply a paradise for bacteria. Nylon dentures are indistinguishable from real teeth. The material contains a dye that gives the dentures a natural look. In addition, the absence of metal fasteners does not indicate the absence of natural teeth. Despite all their advantages, nylon prostheses have a number of disadvantages. Thus, with a low bite, deposits form between acrylic teeth and nylon. This occurs due to the lack of a chemical connection between the teeth and gums. It is with this feature that the need to submit the prosthesis for professional cleaning every two months is associated. Flexible nylon dentures belong to the category of removable dentures of the submersible type, i.e. the transmission of chewing pressure is carried out on the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed with the inclusion of a gingivo-muscular reflex to regulate the chewing process, which is designed to protect the mucosa from overload and, accordingly, allows the development of the desired tone of the masticatory muscles. Not the best reflex, because... disrupts the true physiology of chewing. The normal physiological reflex is a periodontal-muscular reflex, in which the force of contraction of the masticatory muscles is regulated by the degree of sensitivity of the periodontal receptors of the teeth involved in the act of chewing food. The connection of this reflex can only be provided by supported prostheses, i.e. clasps, in which attachments are combined with interlocks; as

well as various support-retaining clasp systems transfer chewing pressure to the remaining teeth within 70-80%. For comparison, for submersible plate prostheses this figure is 15-20%. Another negative factor of flexible dentures is the tight coverage of the alveolar processes and the prosthetic bed, enhanced by the transmission of chewing pressure to the mucous membrane and leading to ischemia (bleeding) of the tissues of the prosthetic bed, which activates the processes of osteoclastification (bone resorption), in simple terms: "The bone is eaten, shrinks", and this sharply worsens the anatomical conditions for subsequent complete removable dentures. Flexible nylon systems are attached to the supporting teeth. If all teeth are missing, the system must be fixed with adhesives, and this brings a constant feeling of discomfort to the patient. Constant loads on the jaw lead to its subsidence. Every year it decreases by about 1 mm. As a result, after 2 years the structure becomes unsuitable for use and has to be replaced. Repair and relocation is practically impossible due to the complexity and high cost of its implementation. Relining a nylon or polypropylene prosthesis is comparable in cost to making a new prosthesis, and the quality of the prosthesis after relining leaves much to be desired. When relining, the base of the prosthesis becomes thicker. And the thicker the base, the less elastic it is! A nylon prosthesis can be adjusted, but after modifications it is poorly polished and over time (after about six months) it loses its smoothness and original color. Meanwhile, the aesthetic component is one of its main advantages. Dental prosthetics with nylon dentures are used for both partial and complete loss of teeth and are one of the most modern methods of removable dental prosthetics in modern dentistry. Today, many analogues of the Valplast material have appeared on the dental materials market, but we use only branded ones, the quality of which has been tested by time. A patented type of nylon, Valplast, was introduced in 1953 in the United States as a plastic for making denture bases with special flexibility properties. It was intended to replace the metal alloys and acrylic combinations used in conventional partial dentures. Installation of orthodontic systems made of nylon is recommended: - in case of loss of one or several units of teeth; - if allergic reactions to various types of metals occur; - if an allergic reaction occurs to prostheses for the manufacture of which acrylic plastic is used; - when the patient has a disease such as periodontitis, which becomes a contraindication to the manufacture of other types of prosthetics; - in cases where the patient does not want to prepare the abutment teeth; - in cases where the patient's profession is associated with a high risk of facial injury. Nylon dentures also have their contraindications for use. Installation is unacceptable if: - when the alveolar ridge is overhanging; - with severe atrophy of the alveolar processes; - with serious defects in the dentition; - at a severe stage of periodontal disease; - in the presence of gingivitis or periodontitis, when the roots are exposed; incorrect crowns that may prevent the installation of the structure; if the gingival edge of the supporting teeth differs in level; with gum atrophy with the formation of a low level.

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